
121. Modelling stellar evolution

I WILL LOOK briefly at the big picture involved in modelling stellar structure and evolution. I will point to some of the areas of stellar physics where Gaia is providing new constraints, and which are contributing to a number of ongoing model refinements.

WHILE THE chemical composition, temperature and pressure deep in stellar interiors are out of reach of direct investigation, their observational consequences in terms of stellar luminosity, surface temperature, radii, masses, surface chemical composition, seismological oscillations, Galactic chemical enrichment, and many others, are nonetheless accessible. Better observations, of course, yield better model constraints.

STELLAR EVOLUTION is driven by changes in chemical composition caused by nuclear reactions. Development of the numerical codes to calculate such models began more than 60 years ago with the pioneering work of Schwarzschild (1958) and Henyey et al. (1959).

Matching stellar models to a wide range of observations has been an extensive and extremely successful field of research over many decades. Continuously improving models combined with many observational advances have led to a progressively deeper understanding of the complex physical processes that occur during the various stages of stellar formation and evolution.

Stellar models are constructed by solving certain basic equations: conservation of mass and of energy, hydrostatic equilibrium, and energy transport via radiation, convection, and conduction. These coupled differential equations have explicit boundary conditions at the stellar centre and at the surface.

Correctly describing the stellar plasma requires extensive inputs from nuclear and particle physics (e.g. opacities and nuclear reaction rates), atomic and molecular physics, thermodynamics, hydrodynamics, and radiative transfer. Convection enters as a phenomenological description involving ‘mixing-length’ and ‘overshooting’, determining not only when a region is unstable to convection, but also the resulting heat transport.

OBSERVATIONAL DATA to constrain stellar models include bolometric luminosities (from magnitudes, distances, and bolometric corrections), surface chemical composition (from spectroscopy), mass (most rigorously for a small number of favourable binary systems), T_{eff} , radius, and oscillation frequencies.

These models have been enormously successful. But increasingly accurate observations provide increasingly challenging constraints. Indeed, various scientific meetings have been devoted to unsolved problems in stellar structure and evolution over the past 20 years (e.g. Livio, 2000; Stancliffe et al., 2007; Neiner et al., 2020).

HIPPARCOS, with its astrometric results published in 1997, provided a significant improvement in distances to 120 000 stars of various spectral types and evolutionary stages. It provided accurate luminosities of many disk and halo stars, open clusters, variable stars, and white dwarfs, which could be compared with the predictions of state-of-the-art stellar evolution models. Better masses, better characterised binary systems, and comprehensive photometric and variability data were also of great value. At the same time, they revealed other modelling problems (Lebreton, 2000).

I should stress that such information was mainly for the nearest stars, typically $\lesssim 100$ pc. The limited distance horizon meant that rarer stages of stellar evolution were absent, while the smaller error on the Hipparcos distances also made the uncertainties on the other fundamental stellar parameters more evident, notably for effective temperatures, abundances, gravities, masses and radii. In short, the Hipparcos distances, along with much other recent observational data, have continued to reveal various shortcomings in existing models (e.g. Buldgen, 2019; Xiong, 2021; Schatz et al., 2022).

In the light of these considerations, the Gaia mission was designed to measure not only positions and motions of two billion stars, but to establish the detailed nature of these objects *at the same time*. In one mission, Gaia provides astrometry, epoch (spectro)photometry in multiple bands, and spectroscopy for the brightest.

I HAVE SUMMARISED the content of the latest Gaia release, DR3, in essay #76. Based only on the first 34 months data, DR3 has astrometry and G band photometry for 1.8 billion sources to 21 mag (a 5-parameter solution for 585 million), mean G_{BP} and G_{RP} photometry (1.5 billion), spectral types (217 million), radial velocities (33 million), variability classification (10 million), rotational velocities (3.5 million), and so on.

While I will focus below on what Gaia will contribute to the modelling of stellar structure and evolution, let me also be clear that many other projects are, or will be, supplying enormous quantities of data too.

Amongst space missions providing high-cadence photometry are Kepler/K2 and TESS, and in the future PLATO. Their high temporal sampling provides accurate asteroseismology data, with PLATO targeting 85 000 solar-like stars, giving radii and masses at 2% accuracy, and ages at around 10% accuracy. Asteroseismology provides parallax-independent distance estimates, allowing tests of stellar evolution and pulsation models.

There are other large time-domain photometric surveys, amongst them OGLE, MACHO, and other microlensing surveys, but also Hipparcos, Pan-STARRS, Sloan (SDSS), and the Zwicky Transient Facility (ZTF). The Vera C. Rubin Observatory will provide multi-epoch multi-band photometry and astrometry in the southern hemisphere, up to 5 mag fainter than Gaia.

Large spectroscopic surveys measuring radial velocities and elemental abundances for large numbers of stars include RAVE, SEGUE, APOGEE, LAMOST, and GALAH. The Gaia-ESO survey at the VLT 8-m telescope is providing large samples of heavy elements abundances, both for s-process and r-process elements.

Instruments under development (e.g. VLT-MOONS, WHT-WEAVE, and VISTA-4MOST) will provide chemical characterisation for millions of stars in the Galactic halo and disk, and chemistry and kinematics for large samples of old red giant branch stars both in the Magellanic Clouds and in the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy.

GAIA IS HAVING a major contribution to the detailed monitoring of stellar populations over a wide variety of (sometimes rare) evolutionary phases.

Amongst its variable stars are 140 000 RR Lyrae stars, along with their periods, amplitudes, mean magnitudes, Fourier components, photometric metal abundances and interstellar absorption (Clementini et al., 2019; Ripepi et al., 2019); 9000 Cepheids (fully characterised and with photometric metal abundances), Long Period Variables, solar-like stars with rotation modulation, as well as δ Scuti, SX Phoenicis, and short period variables (Holl et al., 2018); and 150 000 rotational modulation variables of the BY Draconis class, important for studying stellar rotation, magnetic activity and stellar ages (Lanzafame et al., 2018; Lanzafame et al., 2019).

WHERE DOES this leave stellar modelling? Relevant to the interpretation of present asteroseismic data, several physical mechanisms are still considered to be poorly known, and are not fully accounted for in current stellar models. This includes rotation and rotationally-induced mixing, magnetic fields, tidal effects, thermohaline mixing, gravity waves, mass loss, cross sections such as $^{12}\text{C}(\alpha, \gamma)^{16}\text{O}$, and various others.

On the numerical side, 3D atmosphere models are becoming available. They are providing a calibration of the empirical oscillations and convection parameters used in stellar evolution codes (e.g. Chaplin & Miglio, 2013; Dupret, 2019; Joyce et al., 2019).

Accurate nucleosynthesis predictions, in particular for s-process elements, require a detailed modelling of the asymptotic giant branch evolutionary phase, which is also critical for the interpretation of infrared observations (and extinction) of evolved populations.

Detailed models of the light curves of common envelope binaries are being developed (e.g. Hatfull et al., 2021). In the future, studies of the circumstellar envelopes around massive stars will become possible, exploiting the high resolution of E-ELT in the optical, and the magnetic-field diagnostics of SKA in the radio.

MARCHING ALONGSIDE this explosion in observations, major advances in software infrastructure, computer processing power, and data storage, are transforming how stellar theory, modelling, and simulations interact with and confront these remarkable observations. Examples include Astropy, Athena++, Castro, Dedalus, emcee, Flash-X, GYRE, MAESTROeX, MESA2Hydro, MSG, Phantom, PHOEBE, Skye, Starlib, TARDIS, and TULIPS.

One of the recent initiatives is the ‘open-knowledge’ software ‘Modules for Experiments in Stellar Astrophysics’ (MESA), which started with MESA I in 2013 (Paxton et al., 2013).

The latest version (Jermyn et al., 2023) includes new treatments of time-dependent convection (important during late-stage nuclear burning in massive stars); updates to the treatment of stellar atmospheres, molecular opacities, Compton opacities, conductive opacities, element diffusion coefficients, and nuclear reaction rates; core crystallisation; the treatment of starspots (important for low-mass stars); and modifications for superadiabatic convection in radiation-dominated regions.

JOHN FAULKNER, in his ‘Scientific Legacy of Fred Hoyle’, relates that Hoyle once started a talk by saying, ‘*Oh, basically a star is a pretty simple thing*’. And from the back of the room R.O. Redman muttered, ‘*Well, Fred, you’d look pretty simple too, from ten parsecs!*’.

Gaia is helping to probe what we now know are the great complexities of stars, even from many kiloparsecs!